

USE OF DIFFERENT METHODS IN PREPARING VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS FOR COMPETITIONS

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ABSTRACT: Physical education at the university is a particularly significant part of the educational process, which has a positive effect on the student's general health. The article deals with the influence of physical exercises (volleyball) on the development of physical qualities. Improving the ways and methods of playing volleyball and exercises aimed at developing physical qualities is a topical issue at the present time. Therefore, the purpose of the article is to review the exercises, the implementation of which helps to prepare for the game of volleyball and thus affects the physical quality of students.

KEY WORDS: Physical culture, physical qualities, professional physical qualities, volleyball.

During our many years of research, we have witnessed that the process of training players in the volleyball section of BOSM for volleyball, which is one of the interesting sports, is a unique system.

Because the process of training volleyball players is one of the most difficult pedagogical processes. And this process is constantly improving. One of the important aspects of such improvement is a systematic approach during preparation for competitions. The concept of the system represents the interconnectedness of the elements of volleyball in this process and implies a diverse set of them. It follows that matching all elements and looking at achieving a specific goal as one system ensures the necessary success in comprehensive preparation of volleyball players for competitions. Systematic training of young volleyball players varies from district to district. We consider this as a system from a multi-year point of view, that is, from the initial selection of children at the age of 10-12 to the period of preparation for team formation.

In turn, the training of young volleyball players is independent being a system, it will have its own specific element. The training of young volleyball players is carried out taking into account the supply of reserves to the team that will defend the honor of our independent country in the future.

Organization of the preparatory process for such a system and its structure is characteristic. The arrangement of the system includes the order of the elements, the interdependence of the parts for each system, the level of the systems, and the general condition. When the system is called a structure, it is understood that it is organized according to the purpose of their individual elements. Briefly, the structure of the system is a chain of communication with its elements. Concepts such as "input" and "output" are also characteristic for the system. "Input" refers to raw data, and "output" refers to specific metrics.

Based on the initial data and the nature of the quality of the process, the final result is achieved. A well-organized process does not require proof to show a high result. If the initial

results are good, but the organizational flow is bad, high results cannot be achieved. The preliminary data obtained for the training system of multi-year Olympic reserves in volleyball are input: the contingent of 10-12-year-old volleyball players, the level of coaches, material and technical base.

At the end, it is envisaged to train athletes who meet the requirements for volleyball players in high-level teams and the national team. Thus, any process has an input and an output. In the process of training volleyball players, a systematic approach includes training, competitions and other factors. It is very important to know the level of training of an athlete (complex of indicators, sports results), to choose a set of training methods and tools, to organize training and competition calendar, and to organize all components of the athlete's activity and life.

It takes a long time to solve the task of training volleyball players, and it includes a contingent of volleyball players from 10 to 30 years old. It is necessary to pay great attention to the selection of 10-12-year-old children. Only then, at the age of 18-20, volleyball players record high results.

It should not be forgotten that team character is one of the most important aspects of victory in volleyball. The best interactions between athletes are based on their individual skills. A fixed period of time is required for the players of the team to act with a single goal. Experience shows that it takes several years to achieve high levels of joint action.

The need for many years of training since childhood is based on this, and volleyball is distinguished by its complex technical methods. First of all, this complexity is that all technical methods of the game require touching the ball with the hand in a very short time. Therefore, all technical methods must be effective in a fast-changing game situation. In order to acquire high-level game skills, from childhood, planned and skillful training is required. Long-term training of volleyball players is organized taking into account the age characteristics of the players and taking into account the opportunities at each age level.

It is advisable to start playing volleyball at the age of 11-12 is appropriate. At this age, the level of development of higher nervous activity leads to the successful formation of sports-specific movement skills in children. The game of volleyball is one of the main forms that increase vital activity in children.

The training of volleyball players means the use of factors such as means, methods and conditions to achieve the specified sports performance. The goal of systematic training of players is to train athletes to meet the requirements of the modern volleyball game. During the long-term (8-10 years) preparation process, it is necessary to pay special attention to technical and physical, technical-tactical training and participation in competitions. Teaching game techniques, technical and physical training

The place of technical and physical training is very important during the preparation for competitions. Technical training is a pedagogical process aimed at mastering game methods in an improved way and provides volleyball players with reliable training of game movements. Mastering improved game technique is one of the main tasks of teaching students. In the process of training volleyball players, a systematic approach includes training, competitions and other factors. It is very important to know the level of training of an athlete (complex of indicators, sports results), to choose a set of training methods and tools, to organize training and competition calendar, and to organize all components of the athlete's activity and life.

Technical training is organized in the following sequence;

The development of special physical qualities and the development of body systems and organs that bear the main load during the execution of the studied technical method (general and preparatory exercises). Acquisition of separate elements (auxiliary exercises) that make up the technical method. For example, during an attack shot, this acceleration is 2-3 steps, and when landing on both feet, a vertical rise, raising the arm and executing a movement to hit the ball at a comfortable point of the jump. Add technical method parts (technical exercises) to master technical methods. For example, hitting the ball with full coordination; attack the ball thrown by the teacher.

Knowing how to use technical methods and their types appropriately, taking into account the specific game situation. It is necessary to take into account the individual characteristics of students when improving the technique. Several movements are included in volleyball techniques: acceleration and jumping when attacking and blocking, falling when receiving the ball, etc. It should not be forgotten that on the basis of getting to the ball on time lies the psychological-physiological mechanism of several functions of the difficult organism; aiming (orientation), movement reaction, ability to quickly get out of difficult situations in movement and speed. Therefore, this section requires not only to be attentive, but also to be creative in choosing special tools.

This is useful in the development of special qualities of students. Vitalizing exercises. The tools of this section are based on the usual running and action games. At the beginning, exercises should be used to strengthen the running step. For this purpose, run straight, run with knees raised high, run alternately, run with jumps from foot to foot, run forward with back.

Preparatory exercises. The exercises that prepare oneself depending on the type of movement are divided into exercises that ensure the development of the speed of the movement reaction, combined with the development of observation, and ensure the speed of the response movements, and exercises that ensure the development of the speed of the movements.

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